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3 **Numerical simulations of a tornadic supercell over the**
4 **Mediterranean**

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19

20 **Abstract**

21 On 28 November 2012, a multi-vortex EF3 tornado occurred in southeastern Italy causing one
22 fatality and estimated damage of 60 M€. At approximately 1050 LT (0950 UTC), this tornado,
23 which initially formed in association with an apparent supercell thunderstorm over the Ionian Sea,
24 moved inland. The environment where the tornadic supercell developed was characterized by large
25 vertical wind shear in the lowest 1 km of the atmosphere and moderate conditional instability.
26 Mesoscale-model numerical simulations show that it is possible to produce a track, change in
27 intensity, and evolution of a simulated supercell thunderstorm similar to the actual one that spawned
28 the tornado in Taranto, southern Italy. The genesis of the simulated supercell is due to a
29 combination of mesoscale-meteorological features: warm low-level air advected toward the Ionian
30 Sea, combined with mid-level cooling due to an approaching trough, increased the potential
31 instability; the intense vertical shear favored the possibility of supercell development; boundary
32 layer rolls over the Ionian Sea moved in phase with the cells produced by the orography of Calabria
33 to supply ascent, moisture and heat to the convection. An unusual feature of the present case is the
34 central role of the orography, which was verified in a sensitivity experiment where it was reduced
35 by 80%.

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45 **1. Introduction**

46 Although not generally known, there is a rich history of tornado activity in Italy (Peterson, 1998).
47 Recently the occurrence of several intense tornadoes in Italy has produced renewed interest in the
48 phenomena. For example, on 8 July 2015, an EF3 tornado struck an area near Venice, causing one
49 death and 72 injured and completely destroyed a villa dating back to the XVII century (ARPAV,
50 2015). A multi-vortex EF3 tornado hit Taranto, in southeastern Italy, on 28 November 2012, and
51 was responsible for one death and estimated damage of 60 M€ (Miglietta and Rotunno, 2016;
52 MR16). A numerical simulation using the Weather Research and Forecasting model (WRF) of the
53 meteorological causes for the severe weather in this case is the subject of the present study.

54
55 Most studies of tornadogenesis in the Mediterranean have focused on mesoscale and synoptic-scale
56 observations. Bech et al. (2007) found that a mesoscale convergence line in a highly sheared and
57 relatively low-instability environment was responsible for a tornado outbreak near Barcelona in
58 September 2005. Bertato et al. (2003) found the thermal boundary generated by previous storm
59 outflows and their modification by orography could have played an important role for producing a
60 tornado in the foothills of northeastern Italy. Similarly, Aran et al. (2009) identified a low-level
61 thermal boundary, related to warm-air advection, evaporational cooling due to precipitation and
62 differential cooling due to cloud cover, in the environment where a F2 tornado developed in
63 Catalonia. Mateo et al. (2009) found that the convergence lines induced by the local orography were
64 probably the main factor in a tornado outbreak in northeastern Spain. Nastos and Matsangouras
65 (2014) identified specific synoptic weather patterns favorable for tornado occurrence in western
66 Greece. A comprehensive documentation of tornadoes over Europe can be found in Antonescu et al.
67 (2016).

68
69 Synoptic and observational analyses are valuable for identifying environments favorable for
70 supercells. Additionally, high-resolution simulations by means of limited-area meteorological

71 models (LAMs) may help understand the mechanisms of triggering and development of the
72 supercells and to explore their sensitivity to different parameters. The growth in computational
73 resources combined with more accurate LAMs has allowed the reduction of the typical horizontal
74 grid spacing down to $O(1 \text{ km})$ even for operational runs. However, as the predictability limit for
75 individual convective-scale elements is at most a few hours (Lilly, 1990), in the absence of strong
76 forcing the precise location and timing of convection may be difficult to simulate at a lead time of
77 more than an hour or so, even at such high spatial resolution. Fortunately, in many cases severe
78 convection occurs in association with larger mesoscale flow features, which may have greater
79 predictability. The use of ensemble forecasts has shown promise in estimating the probability of
80 such convective events (Schwartz et al. 2015). In these cases, although operational-like simulations
81 cannot simulate tornadoes, they can often identify the mesoscale forcing conducive to the genesis of
82 supercells, which are known to produce the most severe tornadoes.

83

84 The need for high-resolution simulations is particularly evident in inhomogeneous environments
85 like that of the Mediterranean basin. Indeed, considering that many tornadoes occur near the
86 Mediterranean coast, which is surrounded by steep mountains, we expect that the interaction with
87 the orography, the land-sea contrast, and the intense air-sea interaction are important in the
88 Mediterranean environment (Lionello et al., 2006), determining significant meso- β and meso- γ
89 scale variations of the relevant instability parameters. This is very different from the more
90 homogeneous, synoptic-scale setting typical for severe convective weather of the U.S.A. Great Plains
91 (Doswell et al., 2012). For example, high-resolution numerical simulations of a tornadic event in
92 eastern Spain (Homar et al. 2003) showed that small-scale terrain features, as well as solar heating,
93 were crucial in forcing intense small-scale circulations favoring the development of severe
94 convection. Recently, Miglietta et al. (2016) noted the evolution of a supercell in northeastern Italy
95 was controlled by the synchronous movement of a tongue of high equivalent-potential-temperature
96 (θ_e) air from the Adriatic Sea with the propagation speed of a supercell. The foregoing are

97 distinctive features of Mediterranean supercells as compared to supercells of the U.S.A. Great
98 Plains, where the pattern of θ_e is generally more homogeneous.

99

100 To our knowledge, there are very few studies dealing with the effect of mountains on supercell
101 triggering and development. In idealized conditions, Markowski and Dotzek (2011) showed that the
102 orography mainly changes the thermodynamic conditions (affecting convective inhibition and
103 relative humidity) as a consequence of the flow over/around the mountain. Bosart et al. (2007)
104 studied a F3 tornado in Massachusetts and found that the topography, and in particular the
105 channeling of low-level flows, conspired to create local enhancements to tornadogenesis potential
106 and to compensate for the increased friction over the orography. Recently, Matsangouras et al.
107 (2012, 2014, 2016) showed, for some tornadoes over Greece, that the presence of steep mountains
108 may represent an important factor for tornadogenesis, by changing the values of some instability
109 parameters compared to a simulation with no orography. Here, the synoptic-scale/mesoscale
110 features responsible for the triggering of the supercell in Taranto are analyzed. We believe this topic
111 is worth of investigation, considering we are not aware of any paper showing that the perturbations
112 induced by a mountain may favor the downstream triggering and the location of a supercell, as
113 found and described in the present study.

114

115 The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 contains a short summary of the available
116 observations. Section 3 describes the present nested-grid numerical simulations pertaining to the
117 meteorological conditions surrounding the Taranto tornado of 28 November 2012, while Section 4
118 provides a synoptic overview for this case. Section 5 describes the results of the numerical
119 experiment in the inner grid, focusing on the mesoscale mechanisms responsible for the genesis and
120 development of the supercells. As the orography of Calabria (at the southernmost tip of Italy)
121 appears to play a key role in triggering convection, an additional experiment with reduced
122 orography is also analyzed. Conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

123

124 **2. Observations**

125 A comprehensive description of the tornado affecting Taranto is discussed in MR16, so only a short
126 overview is provided here. (Fig. 1 identifies the places mentioned here.) Several videos and pictures
127 document this severe weather event and can be easily found on the web. Movies clearly show that
128 the tornado originated over the Ionian Sea, near the port of Taranto, which was still warm at the end
129 of November (the sea surface temperature measured in the area was 18.7°C). Tornado landfall
130 occurred at 0950 UTC (1050 Local Time) near the largest steel plant in Europe, a couple of
131 kilometers from Taranto. A crane weighing several tons was knocked down: unfortunately, the
132 employee working on the crane was killed. In this phase, the tornado reached its greatest intensity,
133 at least EF3 according to an estimation of the degree of damage (McDonald and Mehta, 2006), with
134 a total estimated damage of 60 M€.

135

136 After landfall, the movement of the tornado's parent supercell was observed to slightly change from
137 SSW-NNE to S-N (Fig. 5 of MR16). The track of the associated tornado observed over land can be
138 identified in Fig. 2a (blue and pink dots). The translational velocity of the supercell is estimated to
139 be $\sim 22 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ from the nearby 1200 UTC sounding in Brindisi (Fig. 3a). The funnel width was
140 evaluated as approximately 300 m, with several satellite vortices (Venerito et al. 2013). Moving
141 inland, the tornado weakened only slightly, destroying the canopy of a gas station in the town of
142 Statte, about 12 km north of Taranto, and increased its diameter up to 500 m. Just afterwards, the
143 vortex no longer extended fully to the surface as no damage was reported during the passage of the
144 supercell across the Murge hills (peak altitude of approximately 700 m). However, on the
145 northeastern (lee) side of the Murge hills the supercell intensified again and produced some
146 significant tornadic damage (although weaker than before) near the Adriatic coast. The overall
147 horizontal extent of the over-land track of the supercell was about 50 km and the duration about 50
148 minutes.

149

150 The radar reflectivity mosaic from the Italian Civil Protection Agency shows a series of convective
151 cells elongated in the direction of the 500 hPa wind from the orography of Calabria (Fig. 3b), which
152 thus appears to have played an important role in the event. Another remarkable feature, emerging
153 from the Brindisi sounding at 1200 UTC (Fig. 3a), is the intense low-level wind shear (the wind
154 speed changes from 12 knots at 10 m to 56 knots at about 700 m), so that in the lowest 1 km the
155 storm-relative helicity (SRH) was $553 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and the Energy-Helicity Index (EHI) reached the high
156 value of 2.7. On the other hand, only moderate instability was present in the sounding, as the
157 Convective Available Potential Energy (CAPE) was slightly less than 1000 J kg^{-1} . The extremely
158 high values of surface-to-1-km wind shear in the proximity sounding (about 25 m s^{-1}), combined
159 with the low lifting condensation level (about 700 m), is unusual compared to the soundings of U.
160 S. Great Plains tornadoes [cf. with Fig. 3a in Brooks et al. (2003), and with Fig. 10.13 in
161 Markowski and Richardson (2010)], while it is similar to that of strong/violent tornadoes in the
162 southeast United States (Grams et al., 2012). Also, compared with the only climatology of
163 tornadoes available for Italy (Giaiotti et al., 2007), the sounding in the present case shows some
164 unusual features, such as the largest values of EHI and SRH in the entire dataset, and low-level
165 wind shear twice as large as the mean climatological value for F3 tornadoes.

166

167 **3. Numerical simulations**

168 The Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model, version ARW-3.5.1 (see [www.wrf-](http://www.wrf-model.org)
169 [model.org](http://www.wrf-model.org); Skamarock et al., 2008) is used to simulate the event. WRF is a numerical weather
170 prediction system, which solves the fully compressible, nonhydrostatic primitive equations. Terrain-
171 following-type sigma coordinates are used in the vertical, where here forty levels are employed,
172 with levels more closely spaced near the ground to better resolve the boundary layer (their vertical
173 distance ranges from 58 m in the boundary layer to 600 m in the lower stratosphere). Model output
174 is saved every five minutes to follow in detail the time evolution of the supercell, whose lifetime is

175 approximately one hour.

176

177 Three one-way-nested domains are implemented as shown in Fig. 4. The outer domain covers the
178 southern part of the central Mediterranean (210 x 150 grid points, $dx=9$ km), while the intermediate
179 domain covers southern Italy, Albania and western Greece (271 x 193 points, $dx=3$ km); the inner
180 domain covers the Ionian regions of southern Italy (211 x 271 points, $dx=1$ km). The region
181 affected by the supercell is in the middle of the inner domain, and on the east side of the two coarser
182 domains, considering that the propagation of the synoptic-scale features is from the west.

183

184 Considering the successful simulations of a supercell near the Mediterranean coast (northeastern
185 Italy) discussed in Miglietta et al. (2016), we employ the same parameterization schemes, which
186 include: the Thompson et al. (2008) scheme for microphysics; the Rapid Radiative Transfer Model
187 for longwave radiation (Mlawer et al., 1997) and the Dudhia (1989) scheme for shortwave
188 radiation; the unified Noah model (Niu et al., 2011) for land-surface interactions; Mellor–Yamada–
189 Janjic, a turbulent kinetic energy closure scheme, for the planetary boundary layer (Janjic, 2001);
190 finally, cumulus convection is treated explicitly in all domains.

191

192 Different initial/boundary conditions (the boundary conditions are updated every three hours) were
193 initially tested changing both the large-scale forcing – the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) of
194 the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) versus the Global
195 Forecasting System (GFS) analysis/forecasts – and the initial time for the simulations (0000 UTC
196 and 1200 UTC, 27 November 2012; 0000 UTC, 28 November 2012). The only simulation to
197 reproduce the supercell was the one starting at 0000 UTC, 27 November 2012, forced with the
198 ECMWF IFS analysis/forecasts and only this run will be analyzed in the following. (As discussed
199 in Miglietta et al. (2016), the proper simulation of a supercell in the Mediterranean requires that the
200 small-scale variations in space and time of the mesoscale features responsible for it are properly

201 simulated, so that an ensemble approach appears unavoidable to correctly simulate this kind of
202 event.)

203

204 Other simulations are performed to better understand the role of the orography of Calabria in
205 triggering the supercell. The sensitivity experiments are implemented as the control run but with the
206 mountain height reduced in all domains. In this way, the changes in the inner domain can be
207 ascribed mainly to the contribution of the orography of Calabria, since the evolution of the large-
208 scale weather patterns in the control run is retained.

209

210 **4. Synoptic conditions**

211 Synoptic features are analyzed using the WRF model fields in the outermost domain. Figure 4
212 shows the wind and the potential temperature at 500 hPa at 0900 UTC, 28 November 2012, just
213 before the supercell formed. A cold upper low over the western Mediterranean, approaching Italy
214 from the west, is associated with a southwesterly flow in the Ionian regions of Italy, located on the
215 eastern side of a slightly diffluent trough. As a consequence of the eastward propagation of these
216 synoptic patterns, the local wind speed progressively intensifies up to 30 m s^{-1} during the
217 simulation, while warm air of African origin, affecting all southern Italy at the beginning of the
218 simulation, is confined to the eastern Mediterranean basin. At 09:00 UTC, the Ionian regions are
219 still far from the large-scale pressure trough (and its coldest core) over the Tyrrhenian Sea, though
220 the incoming cold air produces a significant cooling in the mid-troposphere in the few hours before
221 the event.

222

223 Figure 5 shows the synoptic features at low levels, in particular the wind vectors and the equivalent
224 potential temperature (θ_e) at 1000 hPa, together with the wind vectors at 900 hPa (to show that the
225 boundary-layer wind is veering with height) at 0000 UTC (a, top) and at 0900 UTC (b, bottom).
226 Comparing the two panels, one can see the intensification of a south-southeasterly low-level jet (up

227 to 25 m s^{-1}), bringing warm and moist air toward southern Italy, and in particular over the Ionian
228 Sea, ahead of the cold front, which at 0900 UTC appears located near Sardinia. Thus, the
229 combination of warm, humid low-level air and cooler, mid-level air makes atmospheric conditions
230 favorable for potential instability as shown below in Fig. 6 (i.e., it increases the Convective
231 Available Potential Energy (*CAPE*) in the area).

232

233 The alternating warmer and cooler strips simulated on the east side of the warm tongue appear
234 elongated in the direction of the low-level shear (approximately east-northeastward). This pattern is
235 related to convectively induced circulations, i.e. rolls, possibly associated with individual
236 convective cells elongated in shear-parallel direction. Ching et al. (2014) showed that the horizontal
237 variations in these modeled fields are grid-size-dependent, since the grid spacing of O (1 km) is
238 within Wyngaard et al. (2004)'s turbulence "terra incognita".

239

240 To explain why the horizontal convective rolls develop only on the northeastern side of the warm
241 tongue, Fig. 6 shows the vertical sounding in the lower troposphere, from 1000 to 500 hPa, at 0900
242 UTC, simulated at two locations (indicated by the circles in Fig. 5b) respectively southeast of
243 Calabria (38.0°N , 18.5°E) and farther south (35.0°N , 18.5°E), near the African coast. Only in the
244 former point are rolls generated in the simulation. The wind profiles appear similar; in particular,
245 the intense deep-layer shear appears favorable to supercells in both cases. However, there are
246 significant differences in the boundary-layer-temperature and dew-point-temperature profiles. At
247 the northern point (Fig. 6, black solid lines), the air is more humid in the low levels and close to
248 saturation, so that low-level parcels (Fig. 6, cyan solid line) encounter only a small convective
249 inhibition, even in the presence of a shallow inversion at 850 hPa. At the southern point (Fig. 6,
250 black dashed lines), the low-level air is much drier and there is a prominent inversion, which
251 increases convective inhibition (and similarly for the west side of the warm tongue). The difference
252 in the humidity content can be explained considering the longer transit over the sea of the low-level

253 air reaching the northern point, which favors a longer duration of moistening of boundary-layer air
254 parcels, as discussed in Moscatello et al. (2008). The profiles of temperature at an earlier time (0300
255 UTC) show that both points were unstable in the boundary layer (not shown); however, the
256 boundary layer in the northern location was colder, being located farther east of the trough and less
257 affected by low-level warm air advection. In the following hours, both locations were affected by
258 intense warm air advection (cf. Fig. 5a with Fig. 5b); however, only at the southern point was the
259 temperature increase above the boundary layer sufficient to generate an inversion strong enough to
260 inhibit convection, while at the northern point the air remained relatively cooler, so that convective
261 inhibition remains very small.

262

263 **5. Mesoscale analysis**

264 The analysis in the previous section identified a large-scale environment favorable to convection
265 and supercell development. A closer look into the inner model domain is necessary to identify the
266 presence of local forcing, which may have played an important role as well.

267

268 **5.1 Mesoscale environment**

269 Figure 7 shows the 1000 hPa and 900 hPa wind vectors and θ_e , at 0700 UTC (Fig. 7a) and at 1000
270 UTC (Fig. 7b), i.e. just before the tornado landfall; the advection of warm, moist air along the
271 Ionian Sea is apparent and makes the environment more unstable, while E-W oriented bands of
272 warmer (in terms of θ_e) air move northward from the southeastern side of the domain and represent
273 the signature of the previously identified rolls. The intensification of the 900 hPa wind (reaching
274 around 25 m s^{-1}) increases the low-level shear, making the environment very favorable to supercell
275 tornadogenesis.

276

277 The intense northward transport of high- θ_e is modulated by the presence of Calabria, which diverts
278 the low-level jet and the warm-air advection from the northwestern Ionian coast (Fig. 7a). Indeed,

279 the blocking of the southerly flow by the orography produces a weak cyclonic circulation in the lee
280 – at around (39.9°N, 16.25°E) -, separated from the main flow (Smolarkiewicz and Rotunno, 1989).
281 The vortex shedding is consistent with the value of the Froude number Fr , the parameter which
282 roughly estimates the way the flow interacts with the orography (Smith, 1979). Considering $U \approx 15$
283 m s^{-1} as the environmental wind impinging on the mountain, $N \approx 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ the Brünt-Väisälä
284 frequency of the incoming airflow, and $h \approx 2000 \text{ m}$ as an estimate of the mountain height, we obtain
285 $Fr = U/(N h) \approx 0.7$. Since $Fr < 1$, the environmental conditions appear favorable for flow blocking.
286 At 1000 UTC, the region to the north of Calabria orography still appears sheltered from the main
287 flow: the low-level air, although warmer, is still cooler than the air advected by the southerly flow
288 over the sea. Some cooler (light orange) spots in the θ_e field, near the Ionian coast of Apulia, are
289 associated with the outflow of convective cells developing over the sea.

290

291 The presence of these cells can be better identified in Fig. 8, which shows a perspective view of the
292 maximum reflectivity (in dBz) and the 100-m wind at 0830 UTC (a, top) and 1000 UTC (b,
293 bottom). At the earlier time (Fig. 8a), the cells appear aligned in the direction of the low-level shear
294 (west-southwest-east-northeast) as they move northward, extending in a linear pattern from Calabria
295 to the southern tip of Apulia across the Ionian Sea. Inland, some cells are generated by the uplift
296 induced by the orography of Calabria, but at this time they remain confined over the mountain.
297 Later, a series of cells extends north of the Sila mountains, triggered by the orography and advected
298 northward by the lower-to-mid tropospheric wind. At 1000 UTC (Fig. 8b), some cells appear
299 elongated from the Sila mountain toward Taranto, in a way similar to the radar reflectivity
300 observations (Fig. 3b), although the simulation underestimates the areal coverage of the convection.
301 This kind of solution (downwind cells) should be expected from the theory of conditionally
302 unstable flows over the orography (Miglietta and Rotunno, 2009): the ratio of the advective time
303 scale $\tau_a = a/U$ to the convective time scale $\tau_c = h_t/(CAPE)^{1/2}$ (the time that convective elements take
304 to grow and produce rain at the ground) - where U is the wind speed, a the ridge half-width and h_t

305 the tropopause height) – can be calculated considering a profile at a point located upstream of Sila
306 [e.g., in the point (17.0°E, 38.5°N) at 0900 UTC]. We obtain $\tau_a/\tau_c \sim 6$, which means that the
307 environmental conditions favor a regime characterized by quasi-stationary convective cells on the
308 upstream side and a second set of convective cells generated downwind (middle panel of Fig. 8 in
309 Miglietta and Rotunno, 2009).

310

311 The most intense of these cells, the one that is to become the simulated Taranto supercell (identified
312 in Fig. 8b by the area of high dBz approaching Taranto), forms over the sea just in the lee of the
313 orography of Calabria at around 0905 UTC, and progressively intensifies as it moves toward the
314 coastline of Apulia (Fig. 2b). The location of the simulated supercell reaches Taranto only 30
315 minutes later than the observed supercell (1020 UTC vs. 0950 UTC) and just 1-2 km from its track
316 estimated in Fig. 1 of MR16. The simulated supercell translation speed is approximately 24 m s^{-1} ,
317 which is also consistent with the observations.

318

319 The trajectory of the cell can only be easily identified beginning from approximately 30 minutes
320 before landfall (at 0935 UTC). Earlier, one can identify the original cell at 0905 UTC, which then
321 splits four times into a pair of left- and right-movers (Weisman and Klemp, 1982); taking into
322 account this complication, the full track of the storm can be roughly identified by the black line in
323 Fig. 2a. It is remarkable that the model is able to reproduce correctly the track and the timing of the
324 supercell over land as well as its weakening near the Murge hills (where again the simulation shows
325 the splitting of the cell) and the new intensification downstream at around 1100 UTC (Fig. 2b),
326 when some EF2 damage was reported near the Adriatic coast (Venerito et al., 2013).

327

328 Considering that the predictability of convection is generally limited to a few hours, we expect the
329 longer forecasting range in this simulation is associated with the presence of a forcing that the
330 model is able to properly represent. This is discussed in the following Subsection.

331

332 **5.2 Supercell development**

333 In order to better identify the mechanisms responsible for the generation of the supercell, we start
334 by focusing on the time step when the cell appears first (0905 UTC). At that time, the pattern of 800
335 hPa vertical vorticity in Fig. 9, together with the conditions of convective instability in which the
336 cells develop (Fig. 6) and the in-phase vertical velocity and temperature perturbations (not shown)
337 are hallmark of horizontal rolls oriented along the boundary-layer-shear direction, i.e. west-
338 southwest-east-northeast (Brown, 1980, Fig. 5). The cloudwater content in Fig. 9 shows that the
339 vorticity signatures are not associated with deep convection, but with regions of mesoscale ascent
340 confined in the low levels before storm development. At the eastern terminus (black arrow) of the
341 southern line which extends from the Sila mountains of Calabria to the southern tip of Apulia across
342 the Ionian Sea, the cell that will develop into the supercell forms.

343

344 It is well known that convective rolls may play a key role in the transport of energy and moisture
345 upward; in particular, the associated mesoscale ascent may carry warm and moist air from the
346 surface to the top of the boundary layer, so that they may locally promote the triggering of deep
347 convection in the presence of favorable conditions (Weckwerth et al., 1996, 2004). This is what
348 happens in the lee of the Sila mountain, where the low-level circulations induced by the western end
349 of one of these rolls superimpose with the intense upper-level perturbations induced by the flow
350 past the orography of Calabria (see the 700 hPa vertical velocity at 1000 UTC in Fig. 10a).

351

352 At 1010 UTC, just before landfall, Fig. 11 shows that the supercell reaches intense vertical vorticity
353 both at 800 hPa (colors) and 500 hPa (contours), while the other rolls and/or smaller cells, moving
354 along the Ionian Sea (Fig. 8), do not intensify and their vorticity remains confined in the low levels.
355 The upper-level vertical-vorticity couplets (+/-) in the lee of the orography (Fig. 11) are evidence of
356 updrafts in vertical wind shear (essential for supercell dynamics) for the cells triggered by the

357 orography. However, the simulations indicate that only the cell maintained by the roll-associated
358 moisture perturbation can last long enough to develop into a supercell. Figure 12 follows the cell
359 (updraft) that continues to intensify from 0930 to 1010 UTC, and becomes the simulated supercell
360 that makes landfall near Taranto.

361

362 As discussed above and emphasized again hereafter, the supercell develops because the
363 environment is extremely favorable to supercell development (and to tornadogenesis). The region
364 where the supercell forms is characterized by a maximum in the 0-1 km shear (Fig. 7) and 0-3 km
365 shear (Fig. 13a, at 0900 UTC), as it is near the left side of the low-level jet, at the border with the
366 wake induced by the orography of Calabria. Next, as the cell moves over the sea, it remains in an
367 environment favorable to rotation: comparing Fig. 13a with Fig. 13b at 1 hour apart (in the latter
368 panel, the cell can be identified with the small maximum approaching the coast of Apulia), we can
369 see that the cell (whose track is shown in Fig. 2a) remains inside a band of high 0-3 km shear, as
370 both move northward nearly synchronously.

371

372 During its transit across the Ionian Sea, the cell progressively intensifies (Fig. 12). Following the
373 northward extension of the warm tongue, a significant 1-h increase of *CAPE* up to 1600-1800 J kg⁻¹
374 is simulated in the Ionian Sea (cf. Fig. 13c and Fig. 13d). (Note that the simulated *CAPE* in Brindisi
375 is about 1000 J kg⁻¹, and is consistent with the observed vertical profile, suggesting that the Brindisi
376 sounding does not properly represent the environmental conditions associated with the development
377 of the supercell, due to the strong inhomogeneity in the area.) The supercell develops near the
378 border of the warm tongue - in Fig. 14, the supercell can be identified with the contour line of 600
379 hPa vertical velocity near (17.2°E, 39.8°N), just north of the region affected by the highest values.

380

381 **5.3 Role of the orography**

382 The previous analysis suggests that the supercell developed in a complex environment,

383 characterized by rough orography and coastlines. Hereafter, in order to test the hypothesis that the
384 orography played a key role in the generation of the supercell, additional experiments were done
385 with the orography reduced by 80% and 50%. The reduction to 50% has the effect to weaken the
386 convection induced by the mountain, so that the supercell is weaker (maximum updraft helicity of
387 $80 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ compared to $250 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ in the control run) but it is still present in the simulation. A
388 reduction to 20% of the original elevation is required to strongly suppress the orographic convection
389 and the generation of the supercell. Figure 15, which is the equivalent of Fig. 7 in the new
390 experiment, does not show lee-side vortices, since the incoming flow is no longer blocked by the
391 Sila mountain (in the new experiment $h \approx 400 \text{ m}$ while U and N are about the same as before and
392 therefore $Fr > 1$). Thus, a regime of “flow over” the orography is favored; on the other hand, the
393 uplift induced by the orography is sufficient to trigger only weak cells ($h/LFC \approx 1$), which do not
394 show any significant low-level rotation.

395

396 Figure 10 shows the vertical velocity at 700 hPa in the sensitivity experiment (b, bottom) in
397 comparison with the control run (a, top). It is apparent that in the latter experiment the mountain
398 perturbs the flow also far downstream in the Adriatic Sea, where a train of gravity waves is apparent
399 (the presence of mountain waves was particularly clear in the early morning of 28 November), but
400 also on its eastern side over the Ionian Sea, where alternating positive and negative vertical velocity
401 perturbations (red and green stripes perpendicular to the main flow) can be identified in Fig. 10a. In
402 contrast, the case with reduced orography generates very weak perturbations in the vertical velocity
403 (Fig. 10b), producing some weak updrafts only over the Sila mountains and immediately
404 downstream, while weak cells appear over the Ionian Sea. The reduction of the mountain height
405 affects the 0-3 km shear, which is strongly reduced in the sensitivity experiment, mainly due to
406 weaker upper level winds (not shown). This means that the shear responsible for the generation of
407 the horizontal rolls is no longer present and only weak convective cells are generated over the sea.
408 At the same time, the reduced environmental shear is detrimental to the generation of rotation in the

409 cells.

410

411 **6. Conclusions**

412 Numerical simulations are performed with the WRF model for one of the most intense tornado
413 situations in Europe in the last few years, i.e. an EF3 tornado affecting the surroundings of the city
414 of Taranto in southeastern Italy on 28 November 2012. Considering that the grid spacing of the
415 inner grid is 1 km, our focus is on the supercell spawning the tornado in Taranto and not on the
416 tornado itself. The numerical experiment shows that it is possible to reproduce the track, the change
417 in intensity, as well as the timing of the supercell.

418 The genesis of the supercell is due to a combination of mesoscale flow features and topographic
419 flow effects, which are illustrated in Fig. 16:

420 - the mesoscale flow features, high- θ_e low-level air and cold mid-tropospheric air, produce
421 potential instability in the Ionian Sea;

422 - the orography of Calabria (Sila Mountain) plays a key role in triggering convection over
423 the mountain and downstream;

424 - the strong deep- and low-level wind shear produce an environment favorable respectively
425 to supercell and tornado development, with high values concentrated in a band that
426 surrounds the supercell during its evolution. Also, the low-level (boundary-layer) shear is
427 responsible for the generation of convective rolls, which move northward along the Ionian
428 Sea, locally creating conditions even more favorable to the triggering and maintenance of
429 convection.

430 The supercell is triggered where the upper-level perturbations generated by the mountains
431 superimpose with the western end of one of these rolls, which delimits a tongue of very moist and
432 warm air at its northern border. We are not aware that similar mechanisms for supercell triggering
433 were previously identified elsewhere.

434

435 Considering that the predictability of convection is generally limited to a few hours, we believe that
436 the skill of the simulation in representing the supercell development is associated with the key role
437 of the orographic forcing, which the model is able to properly represent. This role was better
438 identified comparing the control run with a sensitivity experiment implemented by reducing the
439 mountain height by 80%. The lower orography has the effect of reducing the orographic uplift and
440 the consequent triggering of convection, and the low-level vorticity in the Ionian Sea, thus the
441 convective rolls.

442

443 Together with the favorable environmental conditions and the orography, other forcing may have
444 affected the development of the supercell. In particular, we believe that the thermodynamic changes
445 induced by the positive sea surface temperature anomaly (Vautard et al., 2016) during the event
446 (around 2°C) enhanced lower tropospheric instability and made deep convection possible even in an
447 unusual period of the year for such events, as the end of November (see for example, Meredith et
448 al., 2015). Additional experiments with modified sea temperature (in progress) will shed further
449 light on this sensitivity, which may also be relevant to analyze from a climate-change perspective.

450

451 The interest in this specific case study is not limited to the peculiar environmental conditions where
452 the tornado developed, but is also related to the recursive occurrence of similar events in southern
453 Apulia. Gianfreda et al. (2005) have documented tornadoes in this region since the 16th century,
454 some of which were very intense. More recently, other events have been identified near the port of
455 Taranto (26 October 2010, 27 January 2011) or along the Ionian coast of Apulia (the EF2 tornado
456 outbreak documented in Monacizzo, Ginosa, and Carosino on 12 November 2014 and the tornado
457 in Gallipoli on 19 November 2013). The analysis of the Italian radar reflectivity mosaic map for the
458 latter two cases, which will be the subject of a forthcoming study, reveals the possible presence of a
459 mechanism of development similar to the one studied here, as it shows a line of convective cells
460 elongated from the Sila mountain in SW-NE direction. Thus, the identification of this pattern can be

461 considered as a diagnostic signal relevant to the possible occurrence and location of such severe
462 events for nowcasting purposes.

463

464 Finally, we hope that the present study may promote the analysis of other severe tornadoes in the
465 Mediterranean basin. Numerical simulations will need to be performed in several cases to analyze
466 the relevant forcing responsible for the generation and intensification of the supercells, identifying
467 the patterns conducive to risk and the existence of possible analogies among mechanisms active in
468 different regions.

469

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477

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595 FIGURE CAPTIONS:

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602 Figure 3: Skew- T diagram in Brindisi at 1200 UTC, 28 November 2012 (a, left) (wind units are in
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606 Figure 4: WRF model simulation, domain 1: Wind vectors (m s^{-1} ; barbs) and θ (K; color scale) at
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615 from 1000 to 500 hPa at 0900 UTC, simulated at two locations (shown in Fig. 5b by “O”)
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633 Figure 11: WRF model simulation, domain 3: Vertical vorticity at 800 hPa (s^{-1} ; color scale) and at
634 500 hPa (dashed contours for -0.008, -0.005, -0.002; solid contours for 0.002, 0.005, 0.008 s^{-1}) at
635 1010 UTC, 28 November 2012, at the time when the cell reaches its maximum intensity. The
636 location of the tornado landfall is indicated by “O”.

637 Figure 12: the evolution of the supercell from 0930 UTC to 1010 UTC as illustrated by the contour
638 of w at 500 hPa = 6 m s^{-1} (red) and the vertical vorticity contours ($4, 8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, black; $-4, -8 \times 10^{-3}$
639 s^{-1} , grey) at 500hPa. The colored areas indicate water vapor mixing ratio greater than 7 g Kg^{-1} at
640 800hPa in an approximately 20 km x 20 km square surrounding the growing cells at the indicated
641 times.

642 Figure 13: WRF model simulation, domain 3: 0-3 km wind difference at 0900 UTC (a, left top) and

643 at 1000 UTC (b, right top); Maximum *CAPE* at 0900 UTC (c, left bottom) and at 1000 UTC (d,
644 right bottom). The location of the supercell at 1000 UTC is indicated with an arrow.

645 Figure 14: WRF model simulation, domain 3: θ_e at 1000 hPa (K; color scale) and 600 hPa vertical
646 velocity (contour line = 5 m s⁻¹) at 0930 UTC.

647 Figure 15: As Fig. 7, but for the experiment with orography reduced by 80 %.

648 Figure 16: Schematic diagram of the principal contributing factors to the simulated Taranto
649 supercell: 1) orographic convection over Calabria triggers intense updraft cells, which 2) move
650 downstream in the direction of Taranto, while 3) a heat-and-moisture-supplying, boundary-layer
651 roll, moving in the same direction at about the same speed, comes into phase with one of the cells
652 that 4) grows into a supercell as *CAPE* and vertical wind shear become more favorable. See Fig. 12
653 for definitions of the contours and color shades.

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 777 500 hPa (dashed contours for -0.008, -0.005, -0.002; solid contours for 0.002, 0.005, 0.008 s^{-1}) at
 778 1010 UTC, 28 November 2012, at the time when the cell reaches its maximum intensity. The
 779 location of the tornado landfall is indicated by “O”.

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789 Figure 12: the evolution of the supercell from 0930 UTC to 1010 UTC as illustrated by the contour
 790 of w at 500 hPa = 6 m s^{-1} (red) and the vertical vorticity contours ($4, 8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, black; $-4, -8 \times 10^{-3}$
 791 s^{-1} , grey) at 500hPa. The colored areas indicate water vapor mixing ratio greater than 7 g Kg^{-1} at
 792 800hPa in an approximately $20 \text{ km} \times 20 \text{ km}$ square surrounding the growing cells at the indicated
 793 times.

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796 Figure 13: WRF model simulation, domain 3: 0-3 km wind difference at 0900 UTC (a, left top) and
797 at 1000 UTC (b, right top); Maximum CAPE at 0900 UTC (c, left bottom) and at 1000 UTC (d,
798 right bottom). The location of the supercell at 1000 UTC is indicated with an arrow.

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806 Figure 14: WRF model simulation, domain 3: θ_e at 1000 hPa (K; color scale) and 600 hPa vertical
 807 velocity (contour line = 5 m s⁻¹) at 0930 UTC.

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820 Figure 15: As Fig. 7, but for the experiment with orography reduced by 80 %.

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823 Figure 16: Schematic diagram of the principal contributing factors to the simulated Taranto
 824 supercell: 1) orographic convection over Calabria triggers intense updraft cells, which 2) move
 825 downstream in the direction of Taranto, while 3) a heat-and-moisture-supplying, boundary-layer
 826 roll, moving in the same direction at about the same speed, comes into phase with one of the cells
 827 that 4) grows into a supercell as *CAPE* and vertical wind shear become more favorable. See Fig. 12
 828 for definitions of the contours and color shades.